

A Comparative Study of Lateral Internal Sphincterotomy and 2% Nifedipine and Lignocaine Gel Local Application in the Treatment of Chronic Fissure in ANO

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Abstract:

Introduction: Anal fissures are commonly encountered in routine clinical practice. Anal fissure has traditionally been treated surgically. Developments in the pharmacological understanding of the internal anal sphincter have resulted in more conservative approaches towards treatment. In this study we compare symptomatic relief, healing and side effects of topical 2% Nifedipine and Lignocaine gel and lateral internal sphincterotomy in the treatment of chronic fissure in ano.

Materials and Methods: In this prospective trial, 60 OPD and/or IPD patients with chronic fissure in ano were randomly divided into Group 1 (Nifedipine and Lignocaine gel) and Group 2 (lateral internal sphincterotomy) with 30 patients in each Group. Patients were followed up at weekly intervals for 6 consecutive weeks and biweekly for subsequent 3 months.

Results: Fissure was completely healed in 86.48% of patients in Group 1 and in 100% in Group 2. The mean duration required for healing of fissure was 5.1 weeks in Group 1 and 3.5 weeks in Group 2. 77.46% patients were free from pain in Group 1 whereas 86.28% patients were free from pain in Group 2. No patient had any side effects in either group.

Conclusion: Topical Nifedipine and Lignocaine should be considered as first line treatment in chronic fissure in ano. Lateral Internal sphincterotomy should be reserved for patients with relapse and therapeutic failure to prior pharmacological treatment.

Keywords: Anal fissure, Lateral Internal sphincterotomy.

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Introduction

Anal fissures are considered one of the commonest causes of severe anal pain during defecation. Anal fissure is longitudinal tear in the distal part of anal canal. It is located in the posterior or anterior midline. It extends from the level of dentate line to the anal verge. Acute fissure is presents within 3-6 weeks of symptom onset. It appears of clean longitudinal tear in the anoderm with little surrounding inflammation. Acute fissure usually heals spontaneously within 6 weeks. A chronic fissure, with more than 6 weeks of symptoms, is deeper and has exposed internal sphincter fibers in its base. It is associated with a hypertrophic anal papilla at its upper aspect and sentinel pile at its distal aspect. Based on the etiology it is classified as primary or secondary. Primary is idiopathic. Secondary fissures are those that occur due to some other pathology such as HIV-AIDS, Crohn's

disease, anal tuberculosis. Patients usually present with pain during defecation and passage of bright red blood per rectum. Fissure is mostly due to trauma from the passage of a large hard stool, but it is also seen after acute episodes of diarrhoea. Painful fissures are due to involuntary spasm of the internal sphincter with high resting pressure. Chronic over activity of the internal sphincter could be the cause. Reduction of spasm of anal sphincter causes improvement in blood supply and healing of fissure. Surgical techniques like lateral internal sphincterotomy, effectively heal most fissures within a few weeks [1,2], but may result in permanently impaired anal continence. This has led to the research for alternative non-surgical treatment, and various pharmacological agents such as nitrates (glyceryl trinitrate- GTN, isosbide dinitrate), calcium channel blockers-CCBs like

nifedipine, diltiazem has shown to lower resting anal pressure and heal fissures without the risk of anal continence [3]. The present study compares the effectiveness and side effects of 2% Nifedipine and Lignocaine gel local application and lateral internal sphincterotomy in the treatment of chronic fissure in ano.

Materials and Methods

This prospective, comparative study was undertaken at Mahatma Gandhi Medical College and hospital, Jaipur, India, from December 2023 to June 2024. 60 patients with symptoms of fissure in ano for more than 6 weeks were labelled as having chronic fissure in ano and were enrolled in this study after obtaining an informed written consent. Ethical approval was obtained from the ethical committee of MGMCH.

Inclusion criteria included patients between 18 to 60 years of age of both sexes.

Exclusion criteria included children and elderly patients >60 years, recurrent fissures (already underwent treatment), fissures with hemorrhoids and fistula, fissures associated with malignancies, post chemotherapy and radiotherapy, fissures secondary to specific diseases like Tuberculosis, AIDS, Crohn's disease etc., and pregnant women.

Patients in Group 1 were advised to apply 2- 2.5 cm length of gel thrice daily at least 2 cm into the anus for 6 consecutive weeks. Patients were instructed to wash hands with soap before and after use of gel and apply with the help of nossal.

Cases in Group 2 underwent lateral internal sphincterotomy under spinal anaesthesia. Cases from both Groups were asked to take mild laxatives like cremaffin plus 30 ml at 10pm, high fiber diet and salad, plenty of water- 3-4 litre per day and to do warm sitz bath with betadine 3-4 times a day.

Cases were reviewed in Outpatient Department weekly for 6 consecutive weeks and biweekly for subsequent 3 months. At each visit questions were asked regarding pain relief, control of flatus/feces, and any side effects. Healing was assessed clinically and defined as complete disappearance of fissure. Pain was assessed using a pain score chart graded from 0 (almost pain free) to 5 (severe pain).

Results

In our study most of the cases belonged to age Group 20-30 years [Table/Fig-1] with slight male preponderance [Table/Fig-2]. Majority of the fissures were posterior in location [Table/Fig-3] with sentinel pile present in 42.6% of cases.

Cases were followed up at weekly intervals for 6 consecutive weeks and biweekly for subsequent 3 months. 5 cases from Group 1 and 2 cases from Group 2 were lost to follow up and hence not included in statistical analysis. 86.48% of patients in Group 1 and 100% of patients in Group 2 had completely healed fissures at the end of 4 weeks [Table/Fig-1]. 77.46% of patients in Group 1 who were completely healed with Nifedipine and Lignocaine gel application and 86.28% of patients in Group 2 were free from pain at the end of 3 months [Table/Fig-2].

Three patients in Group 1, whose fissures did not heal after 6 weeks of Nifedipine and Lignocaine application and remained symptomatic, subsequently underwent lateral internal sphincterotomy and fissures healed in 4 weeks after surgery. The mean duration of healing was comparatively longer in Group 1(5.1weeks) than Group 2 (3.5 weeks). No complications were reported in either Group. Comparison between Group 1 and Group 2 did not show any difference in pain relief ($p= 0.5261$) or fissure healing ($p= 0.0679$).

Figure 1: Age Incidence

Figure 2: Sex Incidence

Figure 1: Site of Fissure

Table 1: Healing at 4 weeks

Healing	No. of patients	Percentage
Nifedipine and Lignocaine	24	86.48
Lateral Internal Sphincterotomy	27	100

Table 2: Pain Relief at 4 weeks

Pain free	No. of patients	Percentage
Nifedipine and Lignocaine	17	77.46
Lateral Internal Sphincterotomy	24	86.28

Discussion

Acute and Chronic anal fissures are common problem across the world. It causes considerable morbidity and it adversely affects the quality of life. Anal fissure is usually encountered in young or middle aged adults [4, 5] and is almost equally common in both sexes [4]. It is commonly found in the posterior position (6 o'clock), although anterior fissure (12 o'clock) is comparatively common in

females [6]. Treatment is based on breaking the vicious cycle of pain, spasm, and ischemia is responsible for the development of fissure in ano. Operative management includes dilatation followed by lateral internal sphincterotomy.

Lateral sphincterotomy is the surgery of choice to perform in patients with chronic anal fissure requiring surgical treatment. Postoperative management is easy and rate of healing is faster.

However, complications such as permanent anal incontinence is associated with the surgery. Calcium channel blockers like diltiazem and nifedipine has shown to lower the resting anal pressure [8]. It promotes anal fissure healing at a good rate.[7,9,10]. They are associated with little side effects such as headache and perianal dermatitis [7]. Healing rates of chronic anal fissure in various studies ranged from 48%-82% [3,8,9,11], while that seen in our study is 86.48%. Side effects due to Nifedipine and Lignocaine ranged from 0%-10% [3,10,11] in various studies while no patient developed side effect in our study. In contrast to surgery, chemical sphincterotomy with Nifedipine and Lignocaine is reversible and therefore unlikely to have adverse effects on continence. Patients who are hypertensive, diabetic and medically unfit for surgery can be recommended treatment with Nifedipine and Lignocaine Though fissure healing rate is comparatively slower with Nifedipine and Lignocaine, the stress caused by surgery can be avoided and can be treated on OPD basis. Treatment works out to be very cost effective.

Conclusion

Local application of Topical 2% Nifedipine and Lignocaine should be given as the first option of treatment for chronic anal fissure. Lateral Internal sphincterotomy should be done in patients with relapse and therapeutic failure of prior pharmacological treatment.

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